

NITRATION OF THE SULPHIDES OF β -NAPHTHOL AND METHYL SALICYLATE

BY J. W. AIRAN AND D. M. KULKARNI

Sulphides of 2:2'-diacetoxydinaphthyl and 3:3'-dicarbomethoxy-4:4'-diacetoxydiphenyl have been nitrated yielding products having both nitrogen and sulphur in the molecule.

Nitration of 2:2'-dihydroxydinaphthyl sulphide and of 3:3'-dicarbomethoxy-4:4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide was attempted (Hirwe, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 101; Airan, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1940, 9, 115; this *Journal*, 1948, 28, 43) apparently with the intention of replacing the sulphur atom in the sulphide by a nitro group. The object of the present investigation is to nitrate the molecule in such a way that the sulphur atom would remain intact so that after subsequent reduction corresponding amino-sulphides may be obtained.

It has been found that 2:2'-diacetoxydinaphthyl sulphide when nitrated (*vide* experimental) gives a nitro derivative in which both sulphur and acetoxy groups remain intact. Hydrolysis of the compound yields a product which on further nitration gives 1:6-dinitro- β -naphthol. This fixes the position of the earlier nitro group and also indicates the weakening of the sulphur linkage.

3:3'-Dicarbomethoxy-4:4'-diacetoxydiphenyl sulphide, when similarly nitrated, gives a nitro derivative of the sulphide, the hydrolytic product of which unlike the one from the nitro derivative of 2:2'-diacetoxydinaphthyl sulphide remains unaffected on further nitration. When concentrated nitric acid is, however, used as a nitrating agent, 1:4:6-trinitrophenol is obtained. This indicates the position the earlier nitro group occupied in the molecule and also relatively greater strength of the sulphur linkage as compared with that in β -naphthol sulphide.

EXPERIMENTAL

2:2'-Diacetoxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl Sulphide.—2:2'-Diacetoxydinaphthyl sulphide (prepared by the method of Airan and Shah, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1940, 9, 3, 121) (5 g.) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.), cooled in ice and strong nitric acid (*d* 1.4, 25 c.c.) was added carefully with shaking. No visible reaction was observed as long as it was in ice but on allowing the mixture to attain the room temperature (28°) the reaction started. After the reaction was over the resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 208°. It contains both nitrogen and sulphur.

Dilute nitric acid (2*N* to 4*N*) has under similar conditions no action. Concentrated nitric acid (*d* 1.4) without acetic acid as the solvent or medium gives the same product.

Nitration with nitric acid (10 c.c., *d* 1.4) on warming gave copious brown fumes forming a dark red solution. Heating was continued till no more fume was given off. On pouring the product into ice and crystallising, the same nitro compound as above was obtained. It is soluble in chloroform, acetic acid, acetone and benzene, slightly soluble

in alcohol and insoluble in carbon tetrachloride. (Found : C, 58.87; H, 3.35; N, 5.0; S, 6.5. $C_{24}H_{16}O_2N_2S$ requires C, 58.0; H, 3.25; N, 5.69; S, 6.5 per cent).

2:2'-Dihydroxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl sulphide was obtained by refluxing and hydrolysing the acetoxy compound mentioned above (5 g.) by alcoholic potash (1*N*) for 2 hours or strong ammonia (sp.gr. 0.88, 50 c.c.) for 4 hours. It melts at 224°. (Found : S, 7.73. $C_{20}H_{12}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 7.84 per cent). On acetylation it gives the original acetoxy compound.

Nitration of 2:2'-Dihydroxy-6:6'-dinitrodinaphthyl Sulphide.—The above sulphide (0.5 g.) was treated with a mixture of acetic acid (22.5 c.c.) and nitric acid (d 1.4, 2.5 c.c.) and heated till the evolution of brown fumes ceased. On cooling and pouring over crushed ice, a yellow solid, too small to be examined further, separated out. From the red-orange filtrate on concentration yellow crystals of m.p. 194° were obtained and it was found to be 1:6-dinitro- β -naphthol.

3:3'-Dicarbomethoxy-4:4'-diacetoxydiphenyl sulphide (m.p. 94°) was obtained by acetylating 3:3'-dicarbomethoxy-4:4'-dihydroxydiphenyl sulphide, obtained from methyl salicylate and sulphur dichloride (Kundergi *et al.*, *Curr. Sci.*, 1936, 5, 198; *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1937, 6, 82).

3:3'-Dicarbomethoxy-4:4'-diacetoxy-5:5'-dinitrodiphenyl Sulphide.—The preceding sulphide (5 g.) was treated carefully with nitric acid (d 1.4, 15 c.c.) when reaction started with evolution of brown fumes. The product was then warmed to complete the reaction and then poured over crushed ice. The solid product was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid, as light needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 244-45°. (Found : S, 6.50. $C_{20}H_{16}O_{12}N_2S$ requires S, 6.29 per cent). Hydrolysis of this compound by potash (1*N*) for 2 hours gave a crystalline product from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 263-65°. (Found : S, 7.86. $C_{14}H_8O_{10}N_2S$ requires S, 8.04 per cent).

The above compound obtained by hydrolysis (0.5 g.) on nitration with nitric acid (d 1.4, 2.5 c.c.) in glacial acetic acid in the cold and even on warming does not yield any nitrated product, but on warming and using 4 c.c. of concentrated nitric acid, copious brown fumes are evolved and a red solution is formed from which on pouring into cold water and concentrating crystals of 2:4:6-trinitrophenol, m.p. 120°, are obtained.